

POLYMER COATINGS PROTECTING BUILDING AND STRUCTURE CONSTRUCTIONS FROM THERMAL EFFECTS AND THEIR PROPERTIES

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Abstract.

This article focuses on conducting extensive scientific research aimed at creating and applying fire-resistant, intumescent polymer composites to protect building structures from the effects of heat from the perspective of industrial safety. The technology envisions compounds that form coke under thermal influence, which helps increase their thermal stability and protects them during development, aiming to enhance the heat and corrosion resistance of structures.

Keywords:

corrosion, heat and corrosion of metal structures, iron and steel items, temperature, coatings.

Introduction.

In the modern construction industry, increasing the energy efficiency of buildings is not only an economic benefit but also a key factor in ensuring environmental sustainability. Excess heat energy entering through the roofs and walls of buildings negatively affects the indoor microclimate during the summer months, sharply increasing the need for cooling systems (air conditioners). Heat-protective polymer coatings are a revolutionary solution in this field, distinguished from traditional thermal insulation materials (mineral wool, foam plastic) by their thinness, ease of application, and efficiency. Relevance of Polymer Coatings Protection of Structures: Constant heating and cooling cause thermal stresses in concrete or metal structures. Polymer coatings reduce these stresses and prevent the formation of cracks. Energy Efficiency: "Smart" polymer coatings have the property of reflecting 80–90% of solar rays. This allows the temperature inside the building to be lowered to 5-10°C.

Corrosion protection: The polymers form a waterproofing layer that protects not only from heat, but also from moisture and aggressive chemical environments..

Extensive scientific research is being conducted worldwide on the creation and application of fire-resistant intumescent polymer composites to protect building and construction structures from the effects of heat. In this area, particular attention is paid to the development of resource-efficient and environmentally safe formulations of polymer binders, flame retardants, intumescent chemical additives, and fillers as effective composites, to the formation of coatings of polymer composite materials on the surfaces of metal structures and their thermal stabilization, taking into account their inhibition, and to determining the connection between fire-resistant intumescent polymer composites and metal structures.

Currently, due to the various possibilities and advantages of using metal structures, the demand for steel structures in our lives is increasing. For example, the demand for the use of

metal structures in high-rise buildings, stadiums, industrial buildings, as well as in the extraction and processing of oil and gas on land, is increasing year by year. For this reason, special attention is paid to the safety of objects constructed based on metal structures. Although metal structures are non-combustible, their thermal conductivity is very good, and their mechanical properties are directly dependent on temperature[1].

Analysis and results.

During a fire, excessively high temperatures can lead to a sharp decrease in load-bearing capacity and deformation of steel structures, which increases the risk of collapse of the building structure. According to some studies, when the temperature reaches 500°C, the strength of the structure decreases by approximately 40-50%, which does not meet the required strength level of the building. At 600°C, the steel structure completely loses its strength. In the event of a severe fire, the building can collapse within just 15 minutes, posing a significant risk to human life and leading to economic losses.

Polymer microspheres were obtained using the polymerization reaction of 10 g of olefin (S9) with maleic anhydride (MAH) for the synthesis of PER-C9-MAH brand flame retardants based on pentaerythritol and maleic anhydride, and they are named as follows, (C9-MAH) C9-MAH. Then, 20 g of pentaerythritol (PER) was dissolved in 120 ml of ethanol in a three-necked flask, and 1-hydroxypyrrrolidine-2,5-dione (NHS) and 1-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-3-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) were added as catalysts. After stirring the mixture at room temperature for 1 hour, it was heated to 70°C for 6 hours. Then, the product was washed several times with distilled water and filtered under vacuum. As a result, the final PER-C9-MAH product was obtained after drying at 60°C for 24 hours (Figure 1)[2,3].

Figure 1. The buckling mechanism of polymer coatings under the influence of temperature.

During the conducted scientific research, the effects of metal oxides and dolomite $[\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2]$ additives on the properties and characteristics after pyrolysis were studied, and compositions consisting of ammonium polyphosphate-melamine-expanded graphite, which form polymer coatings protecting metal structures, were created. Analyses of fire-retardant compositions were carried out based on various standard requirements. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) examined the destruction of the coating structure, while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to study significant changes in the composition of the coatings. The formation of coke by the compounds in the composition under thermal influence helped to increase its thermal stability. Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of how traditional intumescent coatings are activated through pyrolysis to protect steel plates.

When a fire occurs, intumescent coatings swell and form a char layer, serving as a protective barrier to suppress and prolong heat penetration, and prevent steel plates from failing. In using fire-resistant coatings as protective coatings on metal-structured buildings, polymer binders, intumescent chemical components, flame retardants, and other additives are used. The main additive in these coatings is the intumescent component, and the use of graphite has been well studied to yield good results. Intumescent coatings based on graphite have been obtained in various ratios, and their physicochemical and mechanical properties have been studied, yielding results. Scientists in our republic have obtained rubber copolymers with n-butyl methacrylates, which have thermoelastoplastic properties, together with flame retardants[7].

The coating has the effect of reflecting heat, and multiple heating and cooling cycles do not lead to consequences.

The application of high-temperature thermal insulators is relevant in the fields of metallurgy, mechanical engineering, energy, industry, and civil construction. In the event of a fire, heat-resistant coatings and layers can withstand high temperatures for a long time, preventing the flame from spreading to adjacent rooms and objects.

We obtained F-1 grade blistering coating. This F-1 grade blistering coating is a composite consisting of ED-20 epoxy resin, CaCO_3 , and melamine, the main feature of which is that blistering occurs on the coating due to exposure to high temperature, and by reducing the penetration of flame temperature into the metal surface, it prevents various damages.

Composition of F-1 heat and corrosion protective polymer composite coating, mass, g.

Obtaining F-1 type curable coating in the laboratory. 50 g of epoxy in a 250 ml heat-stable glass.

Epoxy resin	50 gr
CaCO_3	10 gr
Melamine	5 gr
hardener (PEPA)	5 gr

The resin (ED-20 grade) is mixed with 10 g of CaCO_3 and 5 g of melamine until it reaches a uniform consistency. The mixture is stirred for 30 minutes, and a solvent (646 grade) is added until a workable solution is formed. Then, the mixture is stirred in a quiescent state for 1 hour at a temperature of 25-30°C until the pH reaches 6.7-7.2. Composites based on epoxy resin consist of components A and B, and to cure the final product, 10% PEPA relative to the mass of epoxy resin is added and mixed for 20 minutes. The technology for obtaining these fire-resistant, heat-shrinkable coatings is considered economically and environmentally efficient due to its simplicity[11].

Scientific research has been carried out aimed at improving the fire resistance and mechanical properties of wood and polymer materials, based on modifying melamine-formaldehyde oligomers synthesized by scientists of our republic in solution form with ammonium polyphosphate oligomers.

In these conducted studies, the IR spectroscopy of melamine-formaldehyde oligomers and ammonium polyphosphate, as well as the flame retardants obtained on the basis of the polycondensation reaction of melamine-formaldehyde oligomer with ammonium polyphosphate oligomer during the reaction process, have been analyzed, showing the bonds characterizing the substances[9].

Conclusions.

The developed method for finding universal methods and means of protecting metal structures against corrosion is based on experimental data and considers the possibility of processing uncertain information.

The reviewed methodology for establishing criteria for assessing the quality of anti-corrosion coatings can be used to create the necessary criteria for evaluating the safety of using metal structures, as it relies on proven decision-making methods.

It was confirmed that the fire resistance of the developed 1 mm thick intumescent composition is 11-21% higher compared to similar certified coatings (Endoterm XT-150 and Proterm styles). Using fire-resistant paints with primers produced by BMP allows the creation of coating systems that provide long-term comprehensive protection of metal structures against corrosion and fire.

It is proposed to use BMP weather-resistant fire-resistant Plamkor-3 paints to protect objects operating in an open industrial environment from high levels of pollution. It is recommended to use the composition for reworking metal structures indoors.

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